

ALGEBRAS IN THE SPACE OF COLOURS

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Abstract

In this paper we prove that we can use the algebras theory in image processing. In the real three-dimensional space R^3 we consider the set of colours $P = \{ (l, u, v) / l, u, v \in R \}$. We define an internal product operation in set P and with the natural addition and the product with the real scalars we obtain a commutative algebra for the colours. We prove that the colour algebra is a Banach algebra. We will discuss next about the inverse, the conjugate, the minimal polynomial function, the algebraic form and the trigonometric form of colour, the power operation of colour and its matrix representation.

1. Defining the colour algebra

In the real three-dimensional space R^3 we consider the set P of the triplets (l, u, v) that is $P = \{ (l, u, v) / l, u, v \in R \}$. Note that l (**brightness**) is *the achromatic component* of colour, u and v are *chromatic components*, $s = (u^2 + v^2)^{1/2}$ is the colour **saturation**, and $|x| = (l^2 + s^2)^{1/2}$ is the *modulus*.

Next we will organize the set P as a vector space first and then as an algebra. We define the addition of the elements in P by

$$x_1 + x_2 = (l_1 + l_2, u_1 + u_2, v_1 + v_2) \quad (1.1)$$

where $x_1 = (l_1, u_1, v_1)$, $x_2 = (l_2, u_2, v_2)$.

Multiplying with real scalar by

$$ax = (al, au, av) \quad (1.2)$$

where $a \in R$ and $x \in P$.

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It is observed that P forms a real linear space and the following elements

$$\begin{aligned} e_1 &= (1,0,0) \\ e_2 &= (0,1,0) \\ e_3 &= (0,0,1) \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

are its basis.

We now define in the space P the multiplication operation:

$$x_1 \cdot x_2 = (l_1 l_2 - u_1 u_2 - v_1 v_2, l_1 u_2 + l_2 u_1, l_1 v_2 + l_2 v_1) \tag{1.4}$$

It is found by direct calculation that the product defined by (1.4) is **commutative** and **non-associative** and in addition, the element e_1 from the relations (1.3) is a **neutral element** for the multiplication operation:

$$e_1 \cdot x = x \cdot e_1 = x, \quad \forall x \in P \tag{1.5}$$

Finally, it is observed that the product is **distributive** to the left and to the right of the addition, respectively:

$$x \cdot (y + z) = x \cdot y + x \cdot z, \quad \forall x, y, z \in P \tag{1.6}$$

$$(y + z) \cdot x = y \cdot x + z \cdot x, \quad \forall x, y, z \in P \tag{1.7}$$

In this way, the set P was organized as a **third order** algebra over the field of real numbers. Considering the base defined by the relations (1.3) and using (1.4) we obtain the **Cayley** table for the multiplication of the base elements e_1, e_2, e_3 .

$\cdot$	e_1	e_2	e_3
e_1	e_1	e_2	e_3
e_2	e_2	$-e_1$	0
e_3	e_3	0	$-e_1$

The table (1.8)

We will call **the colour algebra**, the algebra P defined by the table above (1.8). The colour algebra is **commutative**, **non-associative** and with an **unit element**.

2. Properties of the colour algebra

Definition 1.

Let be some element x in P which represented in base (1.3) has the form:

$$x = le_1 + ue_2 + ve_3 \quad (2.1)$$

We call *the conjugate* of x the element $\bar{x}$ defined by the relation:

$$\bar{x} = le_1 - ue_2 - ve_3 \quad (2.2)$$

Note: It is immediately clear that

$$x \cdot \bar{x} = (l^2 + u^2 + v^2)e_1 \quad (2.3)$$

Proposition 1.

For any x, y from P there is the relation:

$$\overline{x \cdot y} = \bar{x} \cdot \bar{y} \quad (2.4)$$

The demonstration is obvious.

Definition 2.

The *modulus* of the colour x is defined by the formula:

$$|x| = \sqrt{l^2 + u^2 + v^2} \quad (2.5)$$

It is immediately verified that

$$|x|^2 e_1 = x \cdot \bar{x} \quad (2.6)$$

Definition 3.

In the vector space P we define the *scalar product* for any x, y from P thus:

$$\langle x, y \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(x \cdot \bar{y} + \bar{x} \cdot y) \quad (2.7)$$

It results immediately $\|x\|^2 = \langle x, x \rangle = x \cdot \bar{x} = |x|^2 \quad (2.8)$

Proposition 2.

For any x, y from P there is the inequality:

$$|x \cdot y| \leq |x| \cdot |y| \quad (2.9)$$

Proof:

Let $x = (l_1, u_1, v_1)$ and $y = (l_2, u_2, v_2)$.

We still have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |x| &= \sqrt{l_1^2 + u_1^2 + v_1^2} \\
 |y| &= \sqrt{l_2^2 + u_2^2 + v_2^2} \\
 |x \cdot y|^2 &= (l_1 l_2 - u_1 u_2 - v_1 v_2)^2 + (l_1 u_2 + l_2 u_1)^2 + (l_1 v_2 + l_2 v_1)^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

From the following identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 (l_1^2 + u_1^2 + v_1^2)(l_2^2 + u_2^2 + v_2^2) &= \\
 &= (l_1 l_2 - u_1 u_2 - v_1 v_2)^2 + (l_1 u_2 + l_2 u_1)^2 + (l_1 v_2 + l_2 v_1)^2 + (u_1 v_2 - u_2 v_1)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

it results immediately (2.9).

We have equality when $u_1 v_2 = u_2 v_1$ and hence the following equality

$$|x|^2 = |x^2|$$

and more generally

$$|x|^n = |x^n|$$

Proposition 3.

Colour algebra is a **Banach** algebra.

Proof: It results from the inequality (2.9).

Proposition 4.

Colour algebra is a **Jordan** algebra.

Proof: It is immediately verified that $(x \cdot y) \cdot x^2 = x \cdot (y \cdot x^2)$ (2.11)

Even more generally, we have $(x^n \cdot y) \cdot x^m = x^n \cdot (y \cdot x^m)$ where n and m are natural numbers, and if x admits inverse, n and m can even be integers.

Proposition 5.

Any element $x \neq 0$, $x \in P$ admits an **inverse**.

Proof:

We have to solve the following equation in y :

$$x \cdot y = e_1 \tag{2.12}$$

where $x \in P$ and e_1 is the **unit element**.

It is immediately verified that there is a solution defined by:

$$y = x^{-1} = \frac{1}{|x|^2} \cdot \bar{x} \tag{2.13}$$

But if $x + \bar{x} = 0$ then equation (2.12) has an infinite number of solutions.

Proposition 6.

The elements of the form $le_1 + ue_2$ define an *isomorphic subalgebra* with the algebra of complex numbers over the field of real numbers.

Proof:

The fact that the set $\{le_1 + ue_2\}$ forms a subalgebra is obvious, considering that $e_1e_2 = e_2e_1 = e_2$, $e_2^2 = -e_1$ and $e_1^2 = e_1$. It remains to show that this subalgebra is isomorphic to the algebra of complex number. The bijective application defined by $f(e_1) = 1$, $f(e_2) = i$ and having $f(le_1 + ue_2) = l + iu$ is extended to an isomorphism. Indeed, if

$$f(x_1) = f(l_1e_1 + u_1e_2) = l_1 + iu_1 = z_1 \text{ and } f(x_2) = f(l_2e_1 + u_2e_2) = l_2 + iu_2 = z_2$$

then

$$f(x_1 + x_2) = f((l_1 + l_2)e_1 + (u_1 + u_2)e_2) = (l_1 + l_2) + i(u_1 + u_2) = z_1 + z_2$$

Likewise

$$f(ax) = f(al_1e_1 + au_1e_2) = al_1 + iau_1 = az$$

and

$$f(x_1 \cdot x_2) = f((l_1l_2 - u_1u_2)e_1 + (l_1u_2 + l_2u_1)e_2) = (l_1l_2 - u_1u_2) + i(l_1u_2 + l_2u_1) = z_1z_2$$

With this, the proposition is proved.

Proposition 7.

The elements of the form $le_1 + ve_3$ define an *isomorphic subalgebra* with the algebra of complex numbers over the field of real numbers.

Proof: It proves the same as the proposition 6.

Definition 4.

Let $x \in P$ be given by the formula $x = le_1 + ue_2 + ve_3$.

We will call $Re(x) = l$ **the real part** of x and $Im(x) = ue_2 + ve_3$ **the imaginary part**.

It results the properties for the real scalar a and $x, y \in P$:

$$Re(ax) = aRe(x)$$

$$Im(ax) = aIm(x)$$

$$Re(x + y) = Re(x) + Re(y)$$

$$Im(x + y) = Im(x) + Im(y)$$

$$Re(x \cdot y) = Re(x)Re(y) + Re(Im(x)Im(y))$$

$$Im(x \cdot y) = Re(x)Im(y) + Re(y)Im(x)$$

$$|Im(x)| = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = s, \text{ where } s \text{ is the colour saturation.}$$

3. The trigonometric form for a colour

Let $x \in P$ be some element written in algebraic form $x = le_1 + ue_2 + ve_3$.

If $|x| > 0$ then we will call **the saturation angle**, the angle θ that verifies the equalities

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{l}{|x|} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\sin(\theta) = \frac{s}{|x|} \quad (3.2)$$

If $s > 0$ then we will call *the hue*, the angle h that verifies the equalities:

$$\cos(h) = \frac{u}{s} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\sin(h) = \frac{v}{s} \quad (3.4)$$

If we note with $\rho = |x|$ (3.5)

then a colour x is written with the trigonometric form, thus:

$$x = \rho(\cos(\theta)e_1 + \sin(\theta)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3)) \quad (3.6)$$

From the above formulas, it result the equalities:

$$l = \rho\cos(\theta) \quad (3.7)$$

$$u = \rho\sin(\theta)\cos(h) \quad (3.8)$$

$$v = \rho\sin(\theta)\sin(h) \quad (3.9)$$

Proposition 8.

If $x \in P$ and $x = \rho(\cos(\theta)e_1 + \sin(\theta)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3))$ then

$$x^n = \rho^n(\cos(n\theta)e_1 + \sin(n\theta)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3)) \quad (3.10)$$

where n is a natural number.

Proof:

For $n = 2$, the formula (3.10) results from calculation and then for some n , mathematical induction is used.

Definition 3.

Note with

$$\sqrt[n]{x} = \sqrt[n]{\rho} \left(\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{n}\right)e_1 + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{n}\right)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3) \right) \quad (3.11)$$

root of order n of x .

Proposition 9.

If $x \in P$ and $x = \rho(\cos(\theta)e_1 + \sin(\theta)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3))$ then

$$\bar{x} = \rho(\cos(\theta)e_1 - \sin(\theta)(\cos(h)e_2 + \sin(h)e_3)) \quad (3.12)$$

Proof:

It results from the definition of the conjugate and the formulas (3.7), (3.8) and (3.9).

4. The minimal polynomial of a colour

Starting from the identity $(x - x)(x - \bar{x}) = 0$ we get $x^2 - x(x + \bar{x}) + x\bar{x} = 0$ or

$$x^2 - 2xRe(x) + |x|^2e_1 = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

Thus we found the *annihilator polynomial* for x .

$$f(x) = x^2 - 2xRe(x) + |x|^2e_1 = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

If $Im(x) \neq 0$ then (4.2) is *the minimal polynomial* for x . If x is real, namely $x = \bar{x} = Re(x)$ then from (4.2) we obtain $f(x) = (x - Re(x)e_1)^2$ and then the minimal polynomial is

$$f_1(x) = x - Re(x)e_1 \quad (4.3)$$

In conclusion, if x is real, then the minimal polynomial has degree 1 and if x has a non-zero saturation, the minimal polynomial has degree 2. We notice that the polynomial f_1 has a real root

$$\lambda = Re(x) = l \quad (4.4)$$

while the polynomial f defined by (4.2) has two complex conjugate roots

$$\lambda_{1,2} = l \pm i\sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = \rho\cos(\theta) \pm \rho\sin(\theta) = \rho(\cos(\theta) \pm isin(\theta)) \quad (4.5)$$

5. Matrix representation of a colour

To a colour x , we can associate the matrix X defined as follows:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} l & u + iv \\ -u + iv & l \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l & se^{ih} \\ -se^{-ih} & l \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

The matrix X is orthogonal and has the characteristic equation:

$$X^2 - Tr(X) \cdot X + det(X) \cdot I = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

$$X^2 - 2l \cdot X + (l^2 + s^2) \cdot I = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

For $\bar{x}$, the conjugate of x , we have the matrix

$$X^* = \begin{pmatrix} l & -se^{ih} \\ se^{-ih} & l \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.4)$$

where X^* is the hermitian transpose of the matrix X .

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Abstract Algebra, T. Luchian, Didactic and pedagogical publishing house, 1975.
2. Algebras, Ion D. Ion, N. Radu, Didactic and pedagogical publishing house, 1975.
3. Algebras, I. Creanga, I. Enescu, Technical Publishing House, 1973.
4. Fundamental notions of algebra, I.R. Safarevici, Academy Publishing House, 1989.
5. Polynomials and algebraic equations, L. Panaitopol, I.C. Draghicescu, Albatros Publishing House, 1980.
6. Elements de calcul numerique, B. Demidovitch, I. Maron, Edition de Moscou, 1973.
7. Linear spaces, F. Reza, Didactic and pedagogical publishing house, 1973.
8. Linear analysis on finite dimensional spaces, I Glazman, I Liubici, Scientific and encyclopedic publishing house, 1980.